

SURFACE FLAW SENSITIVITY OF GLASS FIBRES WITH NANO-REINFORCEMENT IN POLYMER COATING

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SUMMARY: The severe surface flaws of brittle materials can be ‘healed’ using coating. Here, we describe an inexpensive and applicable process by which a nanometer-scale polymer coating layer based on styrene butadiene with varied clays and nanotubes, as environmental barrier coating layer, was applied to alkali-resistant glass (ARG) and the E-glass fibres. Our data indicates that the glass fibre with the nanoscale coating shows significantly improved both corrosion resistance to alkali and its mechanical properties. Moreover, an assessment of changes in the fibre surface nanomechanical properties is provided and a strong correlation between the tensile strength, roughness and Griffith fracture predictions is noted.

KEYWORDS: nanocoatings, clays, nanotubes, alkali-resistance, nanoindentation, contact stiffness, roughness, Griffith fracture mechanics.

INTRODUCTION

One of the major problems with brittle materials is that the measured tensile strength is significantly lower than their theoretical values, which is due to preexisting small defects. These surface flaws providing extra stress at the tip of the cracks can lead to stress-corrosion cracking at low stress level. It also was well known that a glass fibre loaded at a stress below its ultimate strength did not show infinite life, but rather failed without warning after some finite time. Surface coating is indicated to protect efficiently the fibre surface against moisture/alkali attack and improve its mechanical properties [1]. This ‘healing’ effect was viewed as a disappearance of the severe surface flaws because of an increase of the crack tip radius, the flaw filled by coating being either elliptical than sharp [2]. Our recent work showed that the tensile strength of glass fibres can be well described by an either single two-parameter or bimodal Weibull cumulative distribution function associated with different sizing systems [3]. Improved mechanical properties and environmental durability can be achieved by applied corrosion protective coatings [4].

Concrete is the most widely used material in the world, but it is an intrinsically fragile porous material with a low tensile or flexural strength. Despite the glass fibre being considered as a reinforcement of cementitious materials for several decades, the limitation of structural applications still remains. The introduction of alkali-resistance glass (ARG) fibres into the cement matrix may not only reduce the critical flaw size and limit crack initiation but also control crack propagation. It was found, however, that the tensile strength and the impact strength of ARG fibre-reinforced cement products still decrease with age due to corrosive reactions between the fibre surface and the matrix. Previously, many attempts have been made

to modify either matrix or fibre by adding fillers [5] or by surface coatings of polymer [6] and carbon layers [7].

With consideration of the wisdom of natural materials, such as bone of human being, a multi-scale reinforced structure and interphase with reinforced fibres is evolved, which can be responsible of both high strength and toughness. Due to the recent nanocomposite birth derived from the incorporation of nanoscale particles, i.e. clays and nanotubes, into polymers, a large amount of work has been done concerning the enhanced mechanical and physical properties of nanocomposites. Research is also focused on mixed composite systems, in which nanoclays and conventional fillers such as glass are combined in the same polymer matrix. However, much less effort has been devoted to improve the barrier properties of corrosion protective nanoscale coatings on fibres in an environment involving moisture, alkaline solutions, and acidic solutions. Considering the tremendous benefit that would be obtained from an improvement of cement-based materials, here we show how to reinforce traditional glass fibres in a highly alkaline environment using coatings containing either organo-clays or nanotubes. AFM, SEM, nanoindentation and single-fibre tensile tests were used to investigate in detail the surface topography and local nanomechanical properties.

METHODS

Materials and Surface Treatments

The control fibres utilized in this work were E-glass fibre (diameters: 20~23 μm) and ARG-IPF fibres (diameters: 12, 15, 17 and 19 μm), made at Leibniz Institute of Polymer Research Dresden. During the continuous spinning process, the ARG fibres were sized by an alkali resistance sizing consisting of silane coupling agent and film formers. We applied surface coatings based on styrene-butadiene copolymer to the control ARG-IPF fibres, since styrene-butadiene dispersions were found to be the most resistant in alkaline solutions in our previous work [4]. Then the organo-clay particles (Nanofil 15, Süd-Chemie AG, Moosburg, Germany) in maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene with an average size of 65 to 130 nm is dispersed in the obtained solution. A quaternary ammonium surfactant and a non-ionic surface active agent were added to the dispersion for homogeneous distribution of the constituents with or without 1 wt% clays. Pyrolysis (600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 60 min) of the coated fibres was used and the measured total weight gain due to the coating is 5.3 wt%. We extracted the fibres in selected highly concentrated aqueous alkaline solution (5 wt % NaOH, pH of 13) at 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for seven days or at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for one day, which is the most aggressive and corrosive condition to the fibre surface [1]. During the continuous spinning process, the E-glass fibres were sized by the silane coupling agent, γ -APS, in conjunction with epoxy film formers and nanotubes (less than 0.5 wt% of coating) in the aqueous spinning bath.

Characterisations

The single fibre tensile measurement was conducted under 65 \pm 2 % RH and 20 \pm 2 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using the Fafegraph ME testing device (Fa. Textechno) equipped with a 100 cN force cell. The test cross velocity is 10 mm/min and the gauge length is 20 mm in accordance with EN ISO 5079. Based on a vibration approach, the fineness of each selected fibre was determined by using a Vibromat ME (Fa. Textechno) in accordance with EN ISO 53812 and ASTM D 1577. An AFM (a Digital Instruments D3100, USA) was used as both a surface imaging tool and a nanoindentation device for measuring contact stiffness and modulus. The topography and phase images of samples were studied in tapping mode. The cantilever (ULTRASHARP NSC15-F/5, MikroMasch, Estonia) has a normal spring constant of 40.9 N/m, a tip cone angle

of 20° , radius of ~ 10 nm and modulus of 160 GPa to assure good imaging resolution and nanometer scale indents. Maximum height roughness (R_{max}) is the difference in height between the highest and lowest points on the cross-sectional profile relative to the center line over the length of the profile within the cursor box ($4 \mu\text{m} \times 4 \mu\text{m}$). Specimens were prepared by fixing separate short fibres on a silicon waver, within a thin layer of pre-coated epoxy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Surface Topographical and Mechanical Properties

We begin by discussing how the fibre surface morphologies are altered on a microscopic level by the concentrated alkaline environmental attacks (Fig. 1). The fairly smooth and featureless surface of control (unsized) sample presents no apparent height differences (Fig. 1a), while the coated fibres with or without clays show the thin and thick coating layer with irregular distribution in all three dimensions (Fig. 1b,c). It is interesting to note that the coated fibre with clays has similar surfaces features before and after extraction, which indicates the coating layer not being fully removed. In contrast, both the control and coated fibres without clay had a microrough porous surface morphology with particles cover the surface after extraction, where zirconia gains on fibre surface might free of corrosion. It seems that not only most of the coating is removed but also the most top layer of glass is chemically corroded, as being discussed further in the following.

Fig. 1: AFM topography images of fibres: (a) control, (b) coating and (c) coating with nano-clay before (top) and after (bottom) extracted in 5 wt% NaOH aqueous solution for 7 days in an ambient environment.

Our nanoindentation tests at a range of indentation forces were made to provide an indication of the variability of the local contact stiffness of the fibre surface (see Fig. 2). The curves of indentation force as a function of distance between the tip and the surface can be used to calculate surface stiffness, which records the cantilever Z-displacement and deflection as the tip approaches/retracts a surface [8]. It can be observed that k increases with increasing indentation depth, while the relationship is not linear because of continuous changes in the

contact area for parabolic shape tip. It is evident from Fig. 2 that surface stiffness within indentation depth (< 6 nm) was strongly affected by both coating nature and alkali extraction.

Fig. 2: AFM determination of contact stiffness vs. indentation depth for the silicon tip on the surfaces of AR-IPF fibres. Variation of the nanoscale surface properties subjected to alkali attack are indicated by the arrows. The contact stiffness, K , is the slope dF/dh of the initial elastic unloading curve which includes contributions from both the specimen and the indenter.

A modified formalism based on equation of Snedden [9] allows a quantitative evaluation of the contact stiffness and modulus of samples. The expression of contact stiffness and modulus is given by

$$k = 2\sqrt{2Rh} \cdot E_r \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{E_r} = \frac{1 - \nu_i^2}{E_i} + \frac{1 - \nu_s^2}{E_s} \quad (2)$$

where R is radius of curvature of indenter tip and ν is Poisson's ratio. E_r is an effective reduced elastic modulus which includes contributions from both the specimen and the indenter. The subscripts i and s refer to the properties of the indenter materials and the specimens, respectively. The properties of the silicon cantilever tip used were as follows: Poisson's ratio $\nu_i = 0.23$; Young's modulus $E_i = 160$ GPa [10]. The values of the Poisson's ratio ν_s of the coating film are presumed to 0.4. Taking into account of above parameters and using Eqn.1, we plotted the best-fit curves of experimental data in Fig. 2, giving the fibre surface moduli of 9.0 GPa and 7.8 GPa for the coating and coating with clay systems, respectively. After alkali treatment, the surface moduli of the coating and coating with clay specimen either increases to 30.7GPa or decreases to 3.9 GPa, respectively. One must note that the calculated modulus values here are generally much higher than the bulk polymer modulus values determined from tensile testing, which were probably affected by viscoelastic creep, which can increase the initial slopes of the unloading curves. In conjunction with the aforementioned topographic imaging observation in the case of fibre with coatings (Fig. 1b), a comparison of these data suggests that the increase of surface stiffness (modulus) which is very close to the that of the control one, provides an additional strong evidence of organic layer being mostly removed. A large amount of scatter appears, further emphasizes a heterogeneous and porous surface structure. It is believed that the constituents of SiO_2 , ZrO_2 , TiO_2 , K_2O , etc. on the glass surface enable different resistance to corrosion by alkali solutions. The reverse is true in the case of fibre with coating and clay, where the modulus

value of the alkali treated sample is apparently reduced. This result is expected, since chemical corrosion or swelling more or less occurring in the remaining polymer coating with clay layer. Overall, the only 1 wt% clay reinforced coating layer is rather alkali-resistant. This enhancement is attributed to the fact that the nanometre-thin sheet-like layers of clays act as obstacles to molecules diffusing towards the AR-IPF fibre surface, extending their path through the coating and, thus, decreasing its permeability to alkali liquids.

Further insight can be obtained from the failure of coating film and pyrolysed fibre surface observation. The dispersion of particles in coatings can be readily established from AFM images. Fig. 3 shows that the fracture surface topography of coating film with clays after alkali treatment consists of many similar shape particles. Random distribution of the particles dispersed in the coating polymer matrix is clearly visible. Consisting of a layered structure of aluminum sandwiched between two layers of silicon, these clays provide high surface areas of contact between the platelet and the polymer matrix. Obviously an appreciable level of platelet content and orientation is required to provide a significant alkali barrier enhancement. In general, layered silicate clays have individual layer thickness on the order of 1 nm with a very high aspect ratio. It is clear that the silicate layers of clay are intercalated because the measured stacked intercalated silicate layers have a thickness of ~ 6 nm and lateral size of 80 nm. Besides measuring surface topography, images of other surface physical properties such as contact stiffness (hardness) and adhesion are measurable with the AFM [8]. Fig. 4 shows the topography images and corresponding contact stiffness image of the pyrolysed fibre surface where the polymer was removed and clay particles remained. The stiffness image were determined by nanoindentation in force volume mode of AFM, in which an array of nanoindentation force-displacement curves were measured across the sample surface at regular intervals with a constant maximum indentation force. The stiffness map was plotted as a gray-scale image, with lighter shades representing deeper indentation depth, in other words, lower contact stiffness. Worth noting is that no apparent difference of the stiffness and surface adhesion force was found between glass fibre and clay particles which exhibit a very similar response to the indentation tip. Consideration of low volume fraction of clay in the polymer, it is not a surprise that the measured localised moduli of coatings with or without clays have similar values.

Fig. 3: AFM topography and section analysis of fracture surface of coating with clay after alkali treatment. Of interest are the vertical and horizontal distances (thickness & radius) of clay particles on the surface have approximately 6 nm and 40 nm, respectively.

Fig. 4: AFM topography of clay on fibre surface after pyrolysis treatment. The insert shows the force volume image in the square region. Also shown are cantilever deflection (force) vs. Z-displacement curves corresponding to indentation at I and II, respectively.

Fibre Mechanical Properties

We then examined whether the surface coating properties could change the tensile characteristics of AR-IPF and E-glass fibres. The effects of environment attacks (5wt% NaOH, at 20 °C for 1 day and 80 °C for 7 days) on the average strength and modulus are compared roughly in Fig. 5. The first observation to be made is that in general a coating and coating with either clays or nanotubes results in a significantly increases of the strength in the range of 30% to 60%. Therefore, surface coating is believed efficiently to improve the mechanical properties of fibres by its ‘healing’ effect, which can be viewed as a disappearance of the severe surface flaws because of the flaw filled by coating and an increase of the crack tip radius. The addition of nanotubes build a strong interaction between coating and fibre surface flaws resulting significant increase in both tensile strength and modulus. In consideration of the inhomogeneously dispersed nanotubes in the coating (not shown here), a further potential enhancement is expected when a well dispersed nanotubes coating is achieved. Secondly, it reveals that the addition of clays does not necessarily mean that the coating layer has higher mechanical properties, and in turn contributes to increased fibre tensile strength, which is consistent with above nanoindentation observation. This can be understood by noting the tensile strength of coating layer. Because the aforementioned fracture surface of coating film has two components, in the bulk polymer and at the clay/polymer interface, the force required for the failure can be derived. The tensile strength of the coating layer with clays can be modeled using a modified ‘rule of mixture’ taking account of interfacial adhesion strength, τ , for the strength of clay/polymer nanocoating layer, σ_c , as a function of clay volume fraction

$$\sigma_c = \left(\frac{\eta L_c \tau}{4d} - \sigma_m \right) V_c + \sigma_m \quad (3)$$

where η is the clay platelet orientation factor which has values between 0 and 1. L_c and d are lateral size and thickness of the stacked intercalated silicate. σ_m and V_c are tensile strength of polymer and volume fraction of particles. The low volume fraction of clays and poor adhesion of the clay to the polymer (interfacial fracture noticed in Fig. 3) results to a comparable tensile strength of coating with and without clays. It is also worth to mention that the failure strain of fibre is far smaller than that of the polymer coating. Therefore, in view of the ‘rule of mixture’

and consideration of the coating polymer, clay and glass fibres as a multi-scale composite, the coating including clay is not expected to have a significant reinforcement contribution. Thirdly, it reveals that the AR-IPF fibres with coating exhibit a very similar strength reduction upon the alkali treatments to the control fibres, while the moduli shifted towards slightly higher values. This shift also occurs in the case of coating with clays after alkali treatment. The reason remains unclear. Finally, it is highlighted to note that the alkali treatment at ambient temperature has marginal and almost no measurable effects to the strength of AR-IPF with clay coating, reflecting the enhanced alkali-resistance of the coating since the solvent uptake is accordingly reduced by the clay platelets. This result is essentially consistent with the AFM surface observation as mentioned previously in this paper. However, the barrier effect from the clays exhibited complete disappearance when the fibres are extracted at 80 °C. This is attributed to the strong solution interdiffusion at high temperature and possible resulted defects from the significantly different parameters of coefficient of thermal expansion of polymer, clays and glass fibres. Behind the aforementioned complex phenomena, it would suggest that different surface corrosion mechanisms exist at different temperatures which are associated with surface coatings and in turn strongly affect both fibre surface and bulk mechanical properties.

Fig. 5: Effect of the alkali treatment on the tensile strength (bars) and modulus (symbols) of AR-IPF fibres. Also shown are results of E-glass fibre (diameter: 20~ 23 μm) with or without coatings reinforced by nanotubes (< 0.5 wt% of coating). Data are mean \pm s.d. from 50 separate single fibre tensile tests.

Fig. 6: Comparison of Weibull plots of fracture probability as a function of tensile strength for AR-IPF fibres with different coatings before(left) and after(right) surface treatments.

To verify the effect of surface properties on the statistical distribution of fibre tensile strength, the classification of fracture can be based on two modes: i) intrinsic failure which is not influenced by either the sizing or surface treatments; ii) extrinsic failure characterized by surface flaws which are strongly surface property dependent. The cumulative probabilities of failure for single and bimodal Weibull distribution function are given by analytical formulae [1]. A detailed description of the experimental data by either single two-parameter Weibull cumulative distribution function (CDF) or bimodal Weibull CDF is shown in Fig. 6. Both the control and fibres with clay coating show well fit of experimental data by either the single or bimodal Weibull distribution functions. However, the bimodal curves are in general more suitable for the description of the nonlinear probability plots than the single Weibull lines for systems after alkali treatment. Clearly, both systems after alkali treatment result to apparently higher shape parameters, indicating a lower heterogeneity. It suggests that the treatments result in additional surface flaws with similar severity.

Fig. 7: Dependence of the fibre tensile strength on the maximum height surface roughness for AR-IPF fibres with different diameters and coatings before and after NaOH surface treatments.

We have shown that a correlation exists between the fibre tensile strength and its surface maximum height roughness. According to the well known linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM), the condition for brittle failure is that the critical stress intensity factor K_{Ic} value (or the plan strain fracture toughness) is equal to the value of the stress intensity factor, K_I , which is dependent on loading conditions and the flaw size. As a first approximation, one can consider that the critical stress intensity factor in mode I, K_{Ic} , of glass fibre is $1 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$ [11]. Here we modelled fibre fractures as externally circumferentially cracked rod in tension where the crack length, a , for surface flaws is assumed to be far smaller than the diameter of the rod. The strength of fibre, σ_e , can be written in the following equations [12,13]:

$$\sigma_e = \frac{K_I}{1.12\sqrt{\pi a}} \quad (4)$$

The dependence of the theoretical tensile strength on the defect size, a up to 300 nm is shown in Fig. 7. Here, we superimposed the experimental data of the maximum height surface roughness (R_{max}) and tensile strength results for fibres with various treatments on the theoretical curves in Fig. 7. One interesting observation is that most points located either below or very closely along the σ_e - a curve predicted by the Griffith fracture criterion. Indeed, the higher the maximum height roughness the bigger the most severe flaws will be present in

the surface layer and, consequently, the lower the expected value of the ultimate tensile strength.

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